

Inter-annual electricity balancing in 100% renewable energy systems assessed through a techno-economic comparison of data series length, e-hydrogen versus e-methane, and multi-objective solutions

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Abstract

Ensuring year-round reliability in 100% renewable energy systems necessitates large-scale inter-annual storage, and its optimal design is challenged by uncertainties in weather data and technology choice. This study performs a comprehensive global techno-economic analysis comparing electricity-based hydrogen and electricity-based methane as storage energy carriers across 22-year and 85-year weather datasets. Results reveal electricity-based methane as the superior economic choice for inter-annual electricity balancing, with a global demand-weighted annualised inter-annual re-electrification storage cost 76% lower than for electricity-based hydrogen, an advantage driven by significantly cheaper underground storage. Furthermore, this research quantifies the critical risk of under-planning. In the curtailment-optimised case, using 85 weather years increases the required variable renewable energy overcapacity by 57% and storage volume by 58%, leading to a cost markup increase of 58-59% on a global demand-weighted average compared to the shorter dataset. The cost-optimised case requires that the demand-weighted average overcapacity increase from 5.2% to 8.1% and the total annualised cost markup of the balancing system from 2.9% to 4.5%. To translate these findings into actionable policy, this work introduces the ‘tau-analogy’, a novel heuristic that systematically identifies balanced and cost-effective solutions on the Pareto front with trade-offs between system cost and inter-annual storage sizing. This research provides a clear outcome on the hydrogen versus methane debate for inter-annual storage and establishes a new benchmark for data robustness in energy system planning, offering a pragmatic framework for designing economically viable and physically resilient future energy systems.

Keywords

Inter-annual storage, 100% renewable energy, Power-to-X, e-hydrogen, e-methane, multi-objective optimisation.

Nomenclature

ACOIAS	Annualised total cost of inter-annual storage
ACOO	Annualised cost of overcapacity
ACOS	Annualised cost of storage
b€	Billion euro
CAES	Compressed air energy storage
cap	Capacity
capex	Capital expenditures
CF	Capacity factor
CH ₄	Methane
crf	Capital recovery factor
e-CH ₄	Electricity-based methane
e-H ₂	Electricity-based hydrogen
e-MeOH	Electricity-based methanol
e-NH ₃	Electricity-based ammonia
ERA5	ECMWF reanalysis v5
FLH	Full-load hours
FTL	Fischer-Tropsch liquids
GT	Gas turbine
H ₂	Hydrogen
HILP	High-Impact, Low-Probability
IAS	Inter-annual storage
IAV	Inter-annual variability
ICE	Internal combustion engine
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
OC	Overcapacity
PtGtP	Power-to-Gas-to-Power
PtX	Power-to-X
PV	Photovoltaics
RE	Renewable energy

SF	Storage Factor
SOC	State of Charge
TMY	Typical meteorological year
UK	United Kingdom
VRE	Variable renewable energy
WACC	Weighted average cost of capital
y	Year

1. Introduction

The global energy transition, catalysed by the imperative to meet the climate targets of the Paris Agreement [1], is fundamentally reshaping power systems worldwide [2], with renewable energy (RE) sources accounting for a record 92.5% of all new power capacity installed globally in 2024 [3]. This transition is characterised by a rapid and large-scale deployment of variable renewable energy (VRE) sources, with solar photovoltaics (PV) and wind power projected to become the dominant pillars of future electricity supply [4–7]. An expanding corpus of scientific literature affirms the technical feasibility and, increasingly, the economic viability of achieving 100% RE systems across multiple energy sectors, including power, heat, transport, and industry [8,9]. As energy systems advance towards high VRE penetrations, the nature of the primary grid integration challenges evolves from managing the economic impacts of resource variability [10] to overcoming complex technical issues such as maintaining voltage regulation, frequency stability, and overall power quality [11,12]. The management of diurnal (day-night) and seasonal (summer-winter) imbalances between VRE generation and energy demand is a well-studied problem [9,13], with a portfolio of established solutions including short-term battery storage [14–16], demand-side management [17–19], sector coupling [20–22], and enhanced grid interconnections [21,23]. However, as the share of VRE in primary energy supply approaches significant shares [5], the more formidable and less-understood challenge of inter-annual variability (IAV) emerges as the principal bottleneck to long-term system resilience [24,25].

IAV refers to the natural, year-to-year variations in weather patterns that dictate the availability of solar and wind resources [26]. These variations, driven by stochastic weather events and multi-year climate cycles [27] can result in prolonged periods of systemwide energy surplus or, more critically, energy deficit [28] that may span across multiple seasons or even consecutive years [26,29]. The failure to adequately plan for these high-impact low-probability (HILP) events [30], such as a sequence of years with low wind speeds (a ‘wind drought’) [31] or reduced solar irradiation [32,33], poses a substantial threat to the reliability and economic stability of a fully defossilised and highly electrified renewable energy system [34,35]. This issue fundamentally alters the paradigm of energy system planning. A 100% VRE system becomes increasingly energy-constrained [36], demanding sufficient volumes of stored energy

to ensure security of supply throughout extended deficit periods [37,38]. This paradigm shift elevates inter-annual storage (IAS) from an ancillary service to a cornerstone of system resilience [37,39], with profound implications for infrastructure investment and risk assessment [40,41].

Despite its criticality, the analysis of IAS is fraught with methodological uncertainties that create significant research gaps. This study identifies and addresses three interconnected gaps at the core of contemporary energy system modelling.

First, a major source of uncertainty stems from the length of the weather datasets used for system modelling. A prevalent practice in energy system analysis is the use of a ‘typical meteorological year’ or a limited historical period of 30 years or less to represent climatic conditions [42,43]. This approach carries a significant risk of systematically under-planning infrastructure and underestimating costs by failing to capture the full statistical range of climate variability [42,44], including HILP events such as multi-year droughts or the effects of major volcanic eruptions [45]. The sensitivity of the techno-economic outcomes of IAS systems to the length of the underlying weather time series remains a critical and under-explored area of research.

Second, a definitive techno-economic assessment to identify the optimal chemical energy carrier for IAS on a global scale is still needed. Power-to-X (PtX) technologies, which convert renewable electricity into different fuels and chemicals, are widely accepted as the key enabler for long-duration energy storage [46–48]. For the specific application of bulk electricity balancing via a power-to-gas-to-power (PtGtP) pathway, electricity-based hydrogen (e-H₂) and electricity-based methane (e-CH₄) have emerged as the leading candidates [47,49]. e-H₂ offers a higher round-trip efficiency, while e-CH₄ benefits from substantially lower storage costs and the ability to leverage existing natural gas infrastructure [50–52]. Although other carriers such as electricity-based ammonia (e-NH₃) and electricity-based methanol (e-MeOH) are viable for specific end-uses, their lower production efficiency and process complexity make them less viable solutions for large-scale, inter-annual electricity storage [53–55]. A robust, direct techno-economic comparison of e-H₂ and e-CH₄ for the IAS application across diverse global regions is largely absent from the literature.

Third, a persistent disconnect exists between the outputs of multi-objective optimisation models and the needs of practical policymaking, as the models provide a spectrum of optimal solutions without a specific recommendation of solutions based on trade-off criteria. Multi-objective optimisations often produce a Pareto front of optimal solutions, illustrating the trade-offs between conflicting objectives such as minimising total system cost and minimising VRE curtailment [52,56,57]. One approach is to focus on the ‘corner solutions’, as done, e.g. by Hasan et al. [57], which are the points of absolute minimum cost or minimum curtailment, leaving policymakers without a clear, systematic method for selecting a balanced compromise from the continuum of options. This gap hinders the translation of complex modelling results into actionable and politically tenable energy strategies.

This study aims to address the aforementioned research gaps through three novel contributions, thereby enhancing the robustness and practical relevance of energy system planning for 100% RE futures. The primary objectives of this study are:

- To evaluate e-H₂ and e-CH₄ as sole energy carriers for inter-annual electricity balancing across 145 global regions, delivering robust findings on the trade-off between hydrogen's higher round-trip efficiency and methane's lower storage cost.
- To directly compare system requirements derived from a conventional 22-year dataset (NASA) with those from an extensive 85-year dataset (ERA5) for 14 representative regions, thereby assessing the risk of systemic under-planning and cost underestimation.
- To introduce the 'tau-analogy', a novel heuristic, that can identify balanced and pragmatic solutions on the cost-overcapacity Pareto front, offering policymakers a systematic method to select compromises that avoid the costly extremes of the optimisation landscape.

By systematically comparing key energy carriers (e-H₂ vs e-CH₄), quantifying the impact of data uncertainty (22-year vs 85-year datasets), and applying a novel decision-making framework (the tau-analogy), this study provides a robust analysis for planning the inter-annual resilience of 100% RE systems. Such a novel analysis and comparison is key to further develop the novel research field of IAS.

2. Literature review

The imperative to manage VRE variability across all timescales is a foundational concept in the transition to 100% RE systems [14,58]. While the literature on short-term and seasonal storage is extensive [59,60], research into the specific requirements for IAS to buffer against multi-year resource volatility is a more recent and rapidly evolving field. Initial studies focused on the benefits of resource complementarity between solar PV and wind power [61]. However, the field has progressed towards sophisticated energy system modelling to quantify the scale and cost of IAS needed to ensure year-round reliability in high-VRE systems [5].

Several key regional studies have laid the groundwork to understand IAS requirements. For the United Kingdom (UK), Cárdenas et al. [38,62] used nine years of weather data to estimate a need for approximately 67 TWh of total storage, with 55 TWh provided by H₂, and highlighted the critical trade-off between installing additional electricity generation capacity (overcapacity) and storage capacity. Expanding on this, Diesing et al. [52], analysing 33 years of wind data for the UK and Ireland, projected a much larger requirement of 300-500 TWh of gas storage, though covering the entire energy system. Their work provided a crucial techno-economic comparison, concluding that an e-CH₄ pathway would increase system costs by a relatively modest 7-8%, whereas an e-H₂ pathway would lead to a more substantial 14-23% cost increase, driven primarily by the higher cost of underground hydrogen storage. Complementing this focus on long-duration storage, a recent study by Öberg et al. [63] for the UK investigated the

interplay between short-duration battery storage and flexible gas turbines, finding that IAV significantly impacts the optimal mix and revenue streams of these short-term flexibility options.

For Germany, Ruhnau and Qvist [37], in a landmark study using 35 years of data, found that while the most intense ‘wind droughts’ last no more than two weeks, the cumulative effect of sequential low-resource periods extends the critical storage duration to twelve weeks, necessitating around 55 TWh of hydrogen storage. A key finding was that optimising a system based on a single ‘average’ year can underestimate the true multi-year storage requirement by more than 50%. Across different countries in Europe, Brown and Hampp [50] analysed a 71-year dataset for the power sector, confirming the need for IAS and proposing e-MeOH as a potential alternative to hydrogen. More recently, Gøtske et al. [64], using 62 years of weather data, demonstrated that highly renewable European energy systems are cost-effective across a wide range of weather conditions but they reinforced the necessity of dispatchable balancing generation or storage to maintain robustness.

A systematic literature review reveals that while these studies are foundational, they are predominantly focused on specific geographies, mainly in Europe, and often analyse a limited set of storage carriers or use weather data periods shorter than the 40- to 60-year lifespan of the infrastructure being planned. As summarised in Table 1, a comprehensive global assessment that directly compares the leading IAS carriers using a robust, long-term weather dataset, represents a clear and critical research gap.

Table 1. A review of key studies on inter-annual variability and storage. Abbreviations: Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES), European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E), ECMWF Reanalysis v5 (ERA5), Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications (MERRA).

Study and year	Region	Weather data (source and length)	IAS carriers analysed	Key finding/cost metric	Optimisation approach
Cárdenas et al. [38,62] (2021)	UK	MERRA and MERRA-2 (9 years)	H ₂ , CAES, batteries	66.6 TWh total storage (55.3 TWh H ₂); cost of ~75.6 GBP/MWh	Cost minimisation
Ruhnau and Qvist [37] (2022)	Germany	ENTSO-E (2020) (35 years) *	H ₂ , bioenergy, etc.	55 TWh H ₂ storage required; multi-year analysis crucial	Cost minimisation
Brown and Hampp [50] (2023)	Europe	ERA5 (71 years)	H ₂ , methanol	Methanol is a viable alternative to H ₂ for IAS	Cost minimisation
Diesing et al. [52] (2024)	UK & Ireland	MERRA (33 years)	e-H ₂ , e-CH ₄	300-500 TWh storage; e-CH ₄ more cost-effective (+7-8% cost vs. +14-23% for H ₂)	Cost minimisation

Gøtske et al. [64] (2024)	Europe	ERA5 (62 years)	H ₂ , biomass, etc.	High RE is robust to weather variability but needs backup	Cost minimisation
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* data on load, generation, and storage reflecting weather pattern

A crucial insight from these advanced studies is that the fidelity of energy system models is fundamentally dependent on the quality and characteristics of the input weather data [24,37,65,66]. The traditional practice of using a single ‘typical meteorological year’ (TMY) or a short series of ‘average’ years is increasingly viewed as a methodological flaw that can lead to a false sense of security [24,42,65]. Such datasets, by their nature, smooth out variability and are statistically unlikely to contain the HILP weather patterns that pose the greatest stress to a high-VRE system [37,67–69]. Zeyringer et al. [24] demonstrated that a power system designed using a single weather year can become “operationally inadequate” and fail to meet decarbonisation targets when subjected to the climate of other years. This confirms that using weather data periods shorter than the 40- to 60-year lifespan of the infrastructure being planned risks a significant underestimation of the physical and financial investment required to guarantee long-term system reliability [24,37,42,70].

For the specific task of storing TWh-scale energy surpluses for inter-annual electricity balancing, chemical energy carriers produced via PtX processes are the only viable options [39,53,71]. The selection of the optimal carrier is governed by a critical techno-economic trade-off between conversion efficiency and storage cost. For a direct PtGtP cycle, e-H₂ and e-CH₄ are the leading candidates [47,52,53,72]. The direct route using e-H₂ (electricity → electrolysis → H₂ storage → re-electrification) offers a higher round-trip efficiency, with typical estimates ranging from 30–44% [50,53,73]. The e-CH₄ pathway introduces an additional conversion step, methanation. This methanation step slightly reduces the overall round-trip efficiency to a range of approximately 30–38% [47,53,72]. Conversely, e-CH₄ holds a decisive advantage in storage and infrastructure costs, as it is fully compatible with the vast and mature global natural gas network [47,52,53,72]. The capital expenditures (capex) of storing energy in widely available geological formations, i.e., salt or rock caverns, is significantly lower for methane than for hydrogen [52,54,72]. This cost differential for the storage component can be substantial enough to offset the efficiency advantage of the direct hydrogen pathway, especially when required storage volumes are in the hundreds of TWh, as shown by Diesing et al. [52]. While other carriers, i.e., e-NH₃ [54,74] and e-MeOH [50,55], are central to defossilising segments such as shipping and chemicals, their application for bulk electricity balancing is less direct [53]. The production and subsequent re-conversion of e-NH₃ and e-MeOH to electricity involve additional process steps and conversion losses, making them less efficient solutions for the specific problem of large-scale IAS compared to the more direct PtGtP pathways of e-H₂ and e-CH₄ [51,53,75].

This review reveals three critical and interconnected research gaps. First, while the importance of using long-term weather data is acknowledged [24,37,76], a direct, quantitative comparison of system requirements derived from a standard multi-decadal dataset versus an extensive, near-centennial dataset across diverse global regions is missing. Second, although the trade-offs between e-H₂ and e-CH₄ are conceptually understood [47,50,53,72], a comprehensive global techno-economic assessment directly comparing them as the leading candidates for IAS, within a multi-storage framework, has not yet been performed. Finally, existing studies typically present optimised ‘corner solutions’ representing either minimum cost or minimum curtailment, but they lack a systematic and transparent framework to help policymakers select a balanced compromise from the continuum of options on the Pareto front. This study aims to close these gaps by providing a robust global comparison of the leading IAS carriers, quantifying the impact of data uncertainty, and introducing a novel heuristic for multi-objective decision-making.

3. Methods and data

This study employs a detailed techno-economic energy system modelling framework to investigate the impact of weather data series length and the choice of chemical energy carriers on inter-annual electricity balancing. The core optimisation algorithm, implemented in MATLAB [77], is adapted from a previously developed framework designed for global IAS analysis, as detailed in Hasan et al. [57]. All energy values presented in this study, unless otherwise specified, are expressed in thermal terawatt-hours based on the lower heating value of the respective energy carrier (TWh_{th,LHV}). The following subsections detail the methodology of this study. Subsection 3.1 introduces the comparative analysis framework, defining the storage technology scenarios (e-H₂ vs e-CH₄) and the weather datasets (NASA vs ERA5) used in this study, and explains the selection of the 14 representative regions. Subsequently, subsection 3.2 analyses the VRE resource variability as captured by the NASA and ERA5 weather datasets. Finally, subsection 3.3 describes the adapted IAS modelling framework, including the IAS optimisation process and the economic assessment methods.

3.1 Storage technologies and dataset scenarios

To systematically assess the research questions, a comparative analysis framework was designed. For an in-depth analysis of the impact of weather data length, 14 representative regions were selected from the 145 global regions of the IAS framework in Hasan et al. [57] to cover diverse climatic conditions, VRE resource archetypes, and demand structure, as detailed in Table 2. The geographical locations of these regions are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Map of the 14 representative regions selected for in-depth analysis of the weather data length impact. Please refer to Table 2 for the region definition.

Table 2. Characteristics and justification for the selection of the 14 representative regions.

Region code	Included countries / areas / states	Justification for selection
FI	Finland	High-latitude case study with extreme seasonal solar variation and advanced integration of bioenergy.
IBE	Portugal, Spain, Gibraltar	Mediterranean climate with excellent solar resources and a pioneer in concentrating solar thermal power.
BRI	Ireland, United Kingdom, Isle of Man, Guernsey, Jersey	Maritime climate with dedicated top-tier offshore wind resources and a mature, interconnected island grid system.
DE	Germany	Leading RE market with high VRE penetration rates and an advanced industrial and regulatory framework.
EG	Egypt	Strategic location with exceptional solar resources and emerging green hydrogen hub with export potential.
CN-N	Beijing, Tianjin, Hebei, Shanxi, Inner Mongolia, Shandong	World's largest energy consumer with a continental climate and extreme seasonality; excellent PV-wind combination.
ID-JV+TL	Java, Timor Leste	Tropical island nation with rapid demand growth; a key test case for a developing economy with distributed geography.
IN-NW	Punjab, Haryana, Delhi, Rajasthan, Chandigarh	Major urban centre with extreme seasonal variations; projected to be one of the largest megacity electricity markets.
AU-W	Northern Territory, Western Australia	Temperate southern hemisphere with high solar potential; isolated grid with excellent wind resources for studying PV-wind complementarity.
KENUG	Kenya, Uganda	Equatorial location with strong year-round solar potential and a mix of geothermal and hydropower resources.

ZAFLS	South Africa, Lesotho	Africa's most developed electricity system, transitioning from coal, with strong solar and wind resource complementarity.
CL	Chile	Exceptional solar resources in the Atacama region paired with a narrow geography creating unique transmission challenges.
BR-SE	Brazil Rio + ES + MG	Coastal tropical environment with growing energy demand and strong complementarity between hydropower and solar resources.
US-CA	California	World-class solar resources and a global leader in RE policy innovation facing significant grid integration challenges.

To systematically isolate the impacts of weather data uncertainty and storage technology choice, a 2x2 scenario matrix has been developed, resulting in four distinct model runs for each of the 14 representative regions. The first factor investigates the two leading chemical energy carriers for the PtGtP pathway. The e-H₂ scenario assumes that e-H₂ is the sole energy carrier for inter-annual electricity balancing. The round-trip efficiency for this pathway (electrolysis → geological storage → re-electrification) is set to 33%, resulting from the efficiencies of the individual process steps, i.e., water electrolysis (70%) and re-electrification in a gas turbine (GT) or internal combustion engine (ICE) (47%) [55]. In contrast, the e-CH₄ scenario assumes that e-CH₄ is the sole energy carrier for electricity balancing. This pathway includes an additional methanation step with an efficiency of 82.1%, which, when combined with electrolysis and re-electrification, results in a lower overall round-trip efficiency of 27% [55,78]. The primary advantage of the e-CH₄ route is the significantly lower capital expenditures for large-scale underground storage compared to e-H₂ [54,79] (cf. subsection 3.3.2).

The second factor addresses the impact of the time-series length of the input weather data. The baseline analysis uses weather data for the years 1984 to 2005 from NASA [80,81], which has been reprocessed by the German Aerospace Centre [82]. This dataset is used to represent a standard multi-decadal analysis. Additionally, the extensive ERA5 dataset [83], covering the 85-year period from 1940 to 2024, is used for the in-depth analysis of the 14 representative regions to quantify the impact of long-term climate variability and the risk of under-planning associated with shorter datasets.

3.2 Renewable energy resource variability

The VRE generation profiles are derived from hourly weather data. Solar PV full load hours (FLH) are calculated using the LUT-PV model according to Keiner et al. [84], while wind power FLH are calculated based on the methodology of Satymov et al. [85]. To account for the combined effect of both resources in a given region's optimised system, a capacity-weighted FLH (FLH_{cw}) is calculated for each weather year y using Eq. (1):

$$FLH_{cw,y} = \frac{Cap_{wind,2050} \cdot FLH_{wind,y} + Cap_{PV,2050} \cdot FLH_{PV,y}}{Cap_{wind,2050} + Cap_{PV,2050}} \quad (1)$$

where Cap_{wind} and Cap_{PV} are the optimised wind power and solar PV capacities for 2050 from Bogdanov et al. [4]. The specific methodology for determining the regional FLH from the ERA5 dataset is detailed in the supplementary material 1. A comparison of the FLH distributions from the NASA and ERA5 datasets for the 14 representative regions is shown in Figure 2. This analysis reveals notable differences in the statistical properties of the two datasets. For wind power, the deviation from the median FLH is largely contained within a $\pm 20\%$ band for most regions in both datasets, although the ERA5 data exhibits a slightly wider spread and identifies different outlier years. For solar PV, the IAV is generally lower than for wind power, but the ERA5 dataset reveals a more homogeneous and often higher deviation from the median compared to the NASA data. These differences in the long-term statistical distribution of VRE resources, particularly the presence of different extreme years and low-frequency patterns in the longer ERA5 dataset, are expected to have a significant impact on the calculated IAS requirements.

Figure 2. Comparison of annual FLH for solar PV (top) and wind power (bottom) across the 14 representative regions, derived from the NASA (1984-2005) and ERA5 (1940-2024) datasets. Please refer to Table 2 for region definitions.

3.3 Inter-annual storage modelling framework

The modelling framework is designed to find a cost-optimal balance between investing in additional VRE generation capacity (overcapacity) and investing in IAS capacity. Via an

iterative optimisation process, security of supply is ensured under the constraints of the entire multi-decade weather time series.

3.3.1 Inter-annual storage optimisation

The core of the model is an iterative algorithm that determines the minimum required storage capacity for a given level of VRE overcapacity. The process is comprehensively detailed in Hasan et al. [57], and a simplified flowchart of the modelling procedure is presented in Figure 3 for clarity.

The model begins with a defined VRE overcapacity level (e.g., 20% above the capacity needed to meet the annual demand). For each year in the time series, the model calculates the annual electricity balance: the surplus or deficit resulting from the difference between VRE generation (including overcapacity) and total electricity demand. Conversely, for each storage carrier (e-H₂ or e-CH₄), the model starts with a storage factor (SF) of zero. The SF is a normalised parameter representing the storage capacity as a multiple of the average annual balance for each storage type. The model simulates the year-by-year evolution of the storage state of charge (SOC), starting from an initial value of 50%. In surplus years, the storage is charged; in deficit years, it is discharged. After simulating the entire time series, the model checks if the SOC dropped below zero at any point. If yes, the SF is increased by an increment of 0.01, and the SOC simulation is repeated. If no, the current SF is recorded as the minimum viable storage factor for that overcapacity level. This entire process is repeated for a range of overcapacity values, e.g., from 0% to 20% in 0.01%_{abs} increments, to map out the Pareto front, illustrating the trade-off between the required SF and the installed VRE overcapacity.

Figure 3. Flowchart of the IAS modelling procedure adapted from Hasan et al. [57]. The framework is applied independently for the e-H₂ and e-CH₄ scenarios to find the minimum viable SF for a given overcapacity, ensuring the storage SOC remains non-negative. Abbreviations: el. – electricity, th – thermal.

3.3.2 Economic assessment and multi-objective solution selection

The annualised cost of storage (ACOS) for all storage types s for each technology (e-H₂ or e-CH₄) is calculated using the capital recovery factor (crf) as shown in Eq. (2) and Eq. (3). The techno-economic parameters for the different geological storage options are detailed in Table 3.

$$crf_s = \frac{WACC \cdot (1 + WACC)^{N_s}}{(1 + WACC)^{N_s} - 1} \quad (2)$$

$$\forall s \in [H_2^{el}, H_2^{utilise}, CH_4, FTL]: ACOS_{IAS,s} = Cap_{IAS,s} \cdot CAPEX_s \cdot (crf_s + OPEXfix_s) + OPEXvar_s \cdot E_{disch,s} \quad (3)$$

where $WACC$ is the weighted average cost of capital (7%), N is the lifetime of the asset, $CAPEX$ is the capital expenditure, $OPEXfix$ and $OPEXvar$ are the fixed and variable operational expenditures, respectively, and E_{disch} is the total energy discharged from storage over the time series.

Table 3. Techno-economic parameters for IAS facilities, based on data from Fasihi et al. [54] and Aghahosseini et al. [79], as compiled by Hasan et al. [57].

Parameter	Unit	H ₂			CH ₄			FTL
		Salt	Rock	Pipeline	Salt	Rock	Pipeline	Tank
Capex	€/kWh _{th,LHV}	1.03	1.99	13.7	0.23	0.45	3.2	0.02
Opex fixed	% of CAPEX	4.0	3.0	1.0	4.0	4.0	2.0	4.0
Opex variable	€/kWh _{th,LHV,disch}	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0.0002	0.0001	0.0001	0
Lifetime	years	50	50	50	50	50	50	50

The annualised cost of VRE overcapacity (ACOO) is calculated based on the additional installed capacity (Cap_{OC}) required beyond the baseline system, as shown in Eq. (4). The techno-economic parameters for solar PV and wind power overcapacity for the year 2050 are provided in Table 4. These values are derived from an installation-weighted average of the individual costs and lifetimes of fixed-tilted PV, single-axis tracking PV, and wind power technologies from 2040 to 2050 with an interval of 5 years, based on the optimised energy mix for each major global region from Bogdanov et al. [4].

$$ACOO = Cap_{OC} \cdot CAPEX \cdot (crf + OPEX_{fix}) + OPEX_{var} \cdot E_{gen} \quad (4)$$

where E_{gen} is the total electricity generated by the overcapacity assets.

Table 4. Representative weighted transition techno-economic parameters for VRE overcapacity in 2050 for major regions [4], as compiled by Hasan et al. [57]. Abbreviations: MENA – Middle East and North Africa, SAARC – South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation.

Category	Unit	Europe	MENA	Eurasia	Northeast Asia	Southeast Asia	SAARC	sub-Saharan Africa	South America	North America
Capex	€/kWh _{th,LHV}	401.2	327.9	482.0	375.6	311.8	313.8	324.3	336.0	440.8
Opex fixed	% of CAPEX	2.8%	2.9%	2.7%	2.9%	3.0%	3.0%	3.0%	2.9%	2.8%
Opex variable	€/kWh _{th,LHV,disch}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Lifetime	years	37.1	39.1	35.2	37.9	39.7	39.5	39.4	39.1	36.3
crf	-	0.076 2	0.075 4	0.077 1	0.075 8	0.075 1	0.075 2	0.075 2	0.075 4	0.076 5

The total annualised cost for all IAS facilities ($ACOS_{IAS,tot}$) is then calculated by summing the costs of the individual storage types, as shown in Eq. (5). Finally, the total annualised cost of the IAS system (ACOIAS), which is the sum of ACOS and ACOO, as defined in Eq. (6).

$$ACOS_{IAS,tot} = ACOS_{H_2R/CH_4R} + ACOS_{H_2U} + ACOS_{CH_4} + ACOS_{FTL} \quad (5)$$

$$ACOIAS = ACOS_{IAS,tot} + ACOO \quad (6)$$

To move beyond the analysis of ‘corner solutions’ (absolute minimum cost vs absolute minimum curtailment), this study introduces and applies the ‘tau-analogy’ as a novel heuristic to identify balanced, pragmatic compromise solutions on the cost-overcapacity Pareto front. This method draws an analogy to the charging curve of a capacitor, where ‘tau’ (τ) represents the time constant at which approximately 63.2% of the total change has occurred [86]. In this study, the curve of ACOIAS is analysed as a function of increasing VRE overcapacity. The first point, the Tau1 (τ_1) solution, is defined as the configuration that achieves 63.2% of the total possible cost reduction between the most expensive (minimum overcapacity) and least expensive (minimum cost) scenarios. Further points representing progressively more cost-optimised systems are also identified: the Tau2 (τ_2) solution corresponds to an 86.5% cost reduction, while the Tau3 (τ_3) solution represents a 95.0% cost reduction, closely approaching the absolute cost optimum. This structured framework builds upon the global techno-economic assessment of Hasan et al. [57] by providing a transparent method for policymakers to select a ‘good-enough’ solution that avoids the high costs of the curtailment-optimised scenario and the high overcapacity required for the absolute cost-optimised scenario.

4. Results

This section presents the techno-economic results of the comparative analysis. Subsection 4.1 details the physical and financial comparison of the e-H₂ and e-CH₄ pathways based on the 22-year NASA dataset. Subsection 4.2 quantifies the impact of using the 85-year ERA5 dataset for the 14 representative regions on the design and cost for the curtailment-optimised and cost-optimised cases. Finally, subsection 4.3 presents the outcomes of the multi-objective tau-analogy.

While this section analyses the key findings, a full set of comprehensive results for all scenarios and regions is provided in the supplementary material to ensure full transparency and facilitate further research. Supplementary material 1 details the specific methodology used for the ERA5 data processing and presents the results of a direct comparison between the NASA and ERA5 datasets for the concurrent 1984-2005 period. The complete numerical output data for all scenarios and regions is available as a comprehensive data repository in supplementary material 2. Finally, supplementary material 3 contains a complete portfolio of all figures generated for this analysis, including all Pareto fronts, storage state of charge charts, and map diagrams.

4.1 Techno-economic comparison of e-hydrogen versus e-methane

The initial analysis focuses on the required physical infrastructure for IAS under the two technology scenarios, as presented in Figure 4. The top left panel of Figure 4 shows that in the e-H₂ scenario, the required IAS capacity for re-electrification totals approximately 27,700 TWh_{H₂,LHV} globally. The highest storage needs are concentrated in major demand centres, particularly in East Asia (China), North America (USA), and the SAARC region (India), where

requirements can exceed 400 TWh_{H₂,LHV}. The top right panel of Figure 4 illustrates the e-CH₄ scenario, which results in a slightly higher global total requirement of approximately 28,300 TWh_{CH₄,LHV} and follows a similar geographical distribution. The bottom panel of Figure 4 reveals the nuanced impact of this technology choice, showing the relative change in required storage capacity when opting for e-CH₄ versus e-H₂. Contrary to the decreasing efficiency, the relative increase in required storage capacity when switching from e-H₂ to e-CH₄ for electricity balancing is modest, ranging from 0% to a maximum of 5%. The most significant increases are observed in parts of Europe, South America, the SAARC region (India) and Southern Africa, while vast regions across North America, Northeast Asia, and Southeast Asia show minimal change. This indicates complex system-level interactions where the energy system adapts to the different properties of the storage energy carriers beyond simple efficiency penalties. Specifically, because methane storage has a much lower capex compared to hydrogen storage, the system is found to be more economical to build a slightly larger physical storage volume rather than investing in the significantly higher levels of VRE overcapacity that would otherwise be needed to compensate for methane's lower round-trip efficiency.

Figure 4. Global storage capacity requirements for inter-annual electricity balancing for the baseline 22-year NASA dataset. Absolute required capacity for the e-H₂ scenario (top left), absolute required capacity for the e-CH₄ scenario (top right), and relative change in required storage capacity when choosing the e-CH₄ pathway over the e-H₂ pathway (bottom). Note the different colourbar scaling for better visualisation.

The economic assessment reveals that the choice of energy carrier has a profound impact on the financial viability of IAS. Figure 5 presents the global economic results, detailing the ACOIAS and the relative cost markup for both the e-H₂ and e-CH₄ scenarios, along with the direct cost reduction achieved by using e-CH₄. In the e-H₂ scenario, the global total ACOIAS amounts to approximately 5412 b€/a. The costs are highest in regions with large energy demands and significant VRE variability, such as China, the United States, parts of Europe, and India, where annual costs can exceed 75 b€. The cost markup, which represents the costs additional to the 100% RE system cost, to implement IAS in 2050, is substantial in the e-H₂ scenario, with a global demand-weighted average of 103.1% for the curtailment-optimised case representing the highest cost among all viable solutions, and reaching over 50% in several regions, i.e., regions in Southeast Asia, the SAARC region, Eastern Africa, Europe, North America, and South America. In stark contrast, the e-CH₄ scenario presents a far more cost-effective solution, with a global total ACOIAS of approximately 1423 b€/a, about 70% lower than for e-H₂. The cost markup for the e-CH₄ scenario is consequently significantly lower, with a global demand-weighted average of 27.4%. The direct comparison between the two pathways underscores the decisive economic advantage of e-CH₄. The relative cost reduction when opting for e-CH₄ over e-H₂ is significant across the globe, with most regions seeing a cost reduction of approximately 74.3%. In key regions across North America, South America, Africa, and Australia, the reduction exceeds 75%. This substantial cost advantage, driven by the lower capex of methane's geological storage, confirms that the e-CH₄ pathway is the more economically viable option for providing bulk inter-annual electricity balancing under the baseline weather assumptions.

Figure 5. Global economic assessment of IAS solutions for the baseline 22-year NASA dataset. ACOIAS for the e-H₂ scenario (top left), ACOIAS for the e-CH₄ scenario (top right), cost markup relative to the total 2050 100% RE system cost for the e-H₂ scenario (centre left), cost markup for the e-CH₄ scenario (centre right), and relative reduction in ACOIAS for choosing the e-CH₄ pathway over the e-H₂ pathway (bottom). Note the different colourbar scaling for better visualisation.

4.2 Impact of long-term weather data on system design and cost

As established in subsection 3.2, the 85-year ERA5 dataset reveals a different and more challenging statistical landscape of VRE resource availability compared to the 22-year NASA dataset. Specifically, the longer ERA5 time series captures a wider range of IAV for wind power, including different and more severe low-wind years that are absent from the shorter dataset. For solar PV, while the year-to-year variability is generally lower, the ERA5 data reveals a more homogeneous and often higher deviation from the median resource availability.

This subsection quantifies how these more pronounced variations and different extreme years found in the ERA5 data directly translate into significant impacts on the optimal physical system design and the resulting financial investment required to ensure year-round reliability for the 14 representative regions listed in Table 2.

4.2.1 Analysis of the curtailment-optimised case

The direct consequences of these pronounced variations on the physical system design are presented in Figure 6, showing the required VRE overcapacity and IAS re-electrification capacity for both the e-H₂ and e-CH₄ scenarios, and comparing the outcomes derived from the 22-year NASA dataset against those from the 85-year ERA5 dataset.

A consistent and significant trend is observed across both technology pathways that use the longer and more variable 85-year ERA5 dataset necessitating a substantially more robust system design. This is first evident in the required VRE overcapacity as the e-H₂ scenario using ERA5 data notably increases the capacity requirement. For instance, considering the minimum curtailment solution, in Germany (DE), the necessary overcapacity rises from approximately 1.1% to 3.1%. Similar cases are observed in regions such as Finland (FI), Northwest India (IN-NW), and Southeast Brazil (BR-SE), where the change in required overcapacity is observed to be >100%. A similar pattern of increased dependency on overcapacity holds for the e-CH₄ pathway. For example, planning with ERA5 data increases the required overcapacity in Finland (FI) from roughly 2.4% to 6.0% (a ~150% increase), while Northwest India's (IN-NW) requirement grows from 1.5% to 3.6% (a ~130% increase). This demonstrates that regardless of the storage medium, the greater variability captured in the longer time series requires a larger surplus VRE generation to ensure system resilience.

The impact on the required physical storage volume is more pronounced. For the e-H₂ pathway, planning with ERA5 data increases the necessary IAS capacity for re-electrification for Germany (DE) from approximately 415 TWh to over 1100 TWh, a relative increase of more than 175%. Similarly, Finland (FI) requires an increase from roughly 80 TWh to 200 TWh, a similar ~150% increase to that observed for the case of VRE overcapacity. This substantial increase in required storage volume is also observed in the e-CH₄ scenario, where the relative increases are of a similar magnitude across all these 14 regions. This finding directly links the more severe or prolonged 'energy droughts' present in the 85-year weather data to a need for a much larger physical storage reservoir to guarantee year-round security of supply. Ultimately, the finding that both VRE overcapacity and IAS capacity requirements substantially increase when using the longer ERA5 dataset confirms that these key physical infrastructure components are systematically underestimated when planning with shorter weather datasets, an effect that is robust across both energy carriers.

Figure 6. Comparison of minimum viable VRE overcapacity and IAS re-electrification capacity derived from NASA versus ERA5 weather data for e-H₂ scenario (two top panels) and e-CH₄ scenario (two bottom panels). The bar plots on the left of each pair show the absolute values for the NASA and ERA5 datasets. The bar plots on the right of each pair show the relative percentage change when moving from the NASA to the ERA5 dataset. Please refer to Table 2 for region definition.

This substantial increase in physical infrastructure directly translates into a significant financial surcharge, as quantified in Figure 7, which presents the economic comparison for the curtailment-optimised case, detailing the absolute ACOIAS and the final system cost markup for both the NASA and ERA5 datasets for the e-CH₄ scenario. As the preceding analysis in subsection 4.1 established that the e-CH₄ pathway is the more economically viable option than the e-H₂ pathway, this section focusses on a detailed investigation of how the choice of weather data length impacts the e-CH₄ scenario. A consistent trend of increased cost is observed when planning with the longer and more variable 85-year ERA5 dataset. For the e-CH₄ scenario, the ACOIAS rises in most regions. For instance, in Germany (DE), the annual cost increases by over 176%, from approximately 13 b€/a to 35 b€/a. Similar substantial increases are observed in Finland (FI), with a rise of over 151%, and Northwest India (IN-NW), with an increase of over 135%.

The final system cost markup, which measures the ACOIAS as a share of the total 100% RE system cost in 2050, shows the same pronounced impact. The markup in Germany (DE) increases from 9% with the NASA data to 24% with the ERA5 data. Finland (FI) and Northwest India (IN-NW) see their cost markups increase by over 150% and 135%, respectively. This demonstrates that the greater variability captured in the longer time series requires both a larger physical system and a significantly more expensive one to guarantee resilience. In absolute terms, the cost increase is most significant in regions reliant on high-cost storage infrastructure. For instance, in Java and Timor Leste (ID-JV+TL), the system's dependence on underground pipelines drives the ACOIAS up by approximately 70 b€. Notably, Western Australia (AU-W) is a key outlier, showing a cost decrease of approximately 13.5% with the ERA5 data. Ultimately, these findings provide clear quantitative evidence of the significant financial surcharges of insufficient capacity when relying on shorter weather datasets.

Figure 7. Comparison of ACOIAS and cost markup in the curtailment-optimisation case derived from the 22-year NASA versus 85-year ERA5 weather data for the e-CH₄ scenario. The bar plots on the left of each pair show the absolute values for the NASA and ERA5 datasets. The bar plots on the right of each pair show the relative percentage change when moving from the NASA to the ERA5 dataset. Please refer to Table 2 for the region definition.

4.2.2 Analysis of the cost-optimised case

The analysis now transitions from the curtailment-optimised case to the cost-optimised case, which represents a practical benchmark for societies aiming for the most economically efficient energy system including inter-annual balancing. Figure 8 details the impact of weather data length on the cost-optimised pathway, comparing the required VRE overcapacity, the resulting ACOIAS, and the final system cost markup for the NASA and ERA5 datasets across the 14 representative regions.

A key characteristic of the cost-optimised solution is its reliance on high levels of VRE overcapacity to minimise the need for storage, effectively managing IAV by generating electricity surpluses. Figure 8 shows that, similar to the curtailment-optimised case, planning with the longer 85-year ERA5 dataset consistently requires a more substantial system build-out. The required VRE overcapacity increases for all 14 regions when using ERA5 data.

The impact on the required VRE overcapacity is highly region-specific. The most extreme increase is observed in Finland (FI), where the necessary overcapacity increases from 6.6% with the 22-year NASA dataset to 17.9% with the 85-year ERA5 dataset, a relative increase of 173%. Other regions, such as Northwest India (IN-NW) and Iberia (IBE), also show a near

doubling of the required overcapacity. In contrast, some regions exhibit much lower sensitivity to the longer time series; for instance, Chile (CL), Egypt (EG), and Western Australia (AU-W) all show an increase of less than 20.0%.

This increase in physical infrastructure directly translates to higher system costs. The ACOIAS, which in this case consists solely of the cost of overcapacity, shows a corresponding increase. While regions with large energy systems, i.e., Northern China (CN-N), Germany (DE), and the UK and Ireland (BRI) experience the largest absolute cost increases (≥ 2 b€ increase), the relative impact is most severe elsewhere. In Finland (FI) and Kenya and Uganda (KENUG), the annualised cost more than doubles, with relative increases exceeding 100%. The final system cost markup reflects these findings. Finland (FI) and Kenya and Uganda (KENUG) face the highest absolute cost markups ($\geq 4\%$ increase in addition to the single-year energy system cost) and relative markup increase by over 100% when planned with the 85-year ERA5 compared to the 22-year NASA dataset.

Figure 8. Comparison of minimum viable VRE overcapacity (top), ACOIAS (centre), and cost markup (bottom) derived from the cost-optimised case of the 22-year NASA versus 85-year

ERA5 weather data for the e-CH₄ scenario. The bar plots on the left of each pair show the absolute values for the NASA and ERA5 datasets. The bar plots on the right of each pair show the relative percentage change when moving from the NASA to the ERA5 dataset. Please refer to Table 2 for region definition.

4.3 Analysis of multi-objective solutions

While the preceding analyses in subsection 4.1 and subsection 4.2 confirm the cost-effectiveness of the e-CH₄ pathway and the significant impact of weather data length, energy system planning ultimately requires moving beyond the corner solutions of either minimum cost or minimum overcapacity. This subsection applies the tau-analogy, as defined in subsection 3.3.2, to the robust 85-year ERA5 results to identify and analyse practical compromise solutions on the cost-overcapacity Pareto front.

The trade-off between minimising ACOIAS and overcapacity is visualised in Figure 9, which presents the cost markup-overcapacity Pareto fronts for both the e-H₂ and e-CH₄ scenarios across three diverse representative regions. The Pareto fronts exhibit a consistent pattern across all regions, characterised by a steep initial reduction in ACOIAS cost markup with the first few percentage points of added VRE overcapacity, followed by progressively diminishing returns as the system approaches the absolute cost optimum. The tau-analogy provides a systematic method to identify key points along this curve.

For the IBE region, the economic advantage of the e-CH₄ pathway is immediately apparent. While the e-H₂ system starts with a cost markup of 77.4% at its minimum overcapacity point with 2.24% overcapacity, the e-CH₄ system's starting markup is 19.4% for the same overcapacity. The tau-analogy effectively identifies compromise points for both; for the e-CH₄ case, the τ_1 solution at 4.26% overcapacity reduces the markup to 10.4%, capturing over half of the total possible cost reduction for a 2-percentage point increase in overcapacity. The trade-off is even more critical for the e-H₂ pathway, where the τ_1 solution cuts the markup by more than half to 31.8%, highlighting the crucial role of moderate overcapacity in avoiding extreme costs.

This trend is consistent in Northwest India (IN-NW), where the starting cost markup for the e-H₂ system is a prohibitive 99.7% at 3.58% overcapacity. The τ_2 solution, however, identifies a more feasible configuration at 6.91% overcapacity that brings the cost markup down to 16.3%. In contrast, the e-CH₄ system already achieves a lower markup of 11.0% at its τ_1 solution with 5.76% overcapacity. The analysis for Kenya and Uganda (KENUG) further underscores the value of the tau-analogy in making high-cost systems tenable. The e-H₂ scenario begins with an extreme cost markup of over 300%, but the τ_2 solution identifies a configuration at 8.9% overcapacity that reduces this burden to 48.0%. This demonstrates that while absolute costs remain higher for the e-H₂ pathway, the trade-off methodology provides a systematic route towards financial feasibility.

Figure 9. Comparison of the cost markup of ACOIAS versus overcapacity for IBE (top), IN-NW (centre), and KENUG (bottom). e-H₂ scenarios are on the left while e-CH₄ scenarios are on the right. Please refer to Table 2 for region definition and note the different y-axis scaling for better visualisation.

5. Discussion

The results presented in this study offer a comprehensive global assessment of the key techno-economic trade-offs in designing IAS systems for 100% RE futures. By systematically comparing the two leading chemical energy carriers for IAS across two distinct weather data time series of different lengths, this research provides critical insights into the challenges and opportunities for ensuring long-term system resilience. The following sub-sections discuss the implications of these findings, focusing on the criticality of data robustness for reliable infrastructure planning, the nuanced criteria for technology selection beyond simple efficiency metrics, and the practical application of multi-objective solutions for effective energy policy.

5.1 Data robustness and planning implications

A primary and unequivocal finding of this study is the profound impact of weather data series length on the design and cost of resilient energy systems. The analysis demonstrates that using the extensive 85-year ERA5 dataset results in systems that require substantially more VRE overcapacity and physical storage volume compared to those planned with the 22-year NASA dataset for all the representative regions except Western Australia (AU-W). For both the e-H₂ and e-CH₄ pathways, the required overcapacity and storage volumes increased by over 100% in Finland (FI), Germany (DE), Northwest India (IN-NW), and Southeast Brazil (BR-SE) when the longer, more variable weather history was considered. This outcome provides a global-scale, quantitative confirmation of a critical issue that has been increasingly highlighted in the literature: planning with shorter, more conventional time series risks a significant underestimation of the physical and financial investment required to guarantee long-term system reliability [24,37,42], a finding consistent with regional studies that also show significant system design changes across different multi-year periods [63].

This finding directly reinforces and globalises the conclusions of Ruhnau and Qvist [37], whose landmark study on Germany showed that single-year system optimisation could underestimate storage needs by more than 50%. The results of this study reveal a similar, systematic underestimation on a global scale. On a demand-weighted average, using the 85-year ERA5 dataset increases the required VRE overcapacity by 57% and the physical storage volume by 58% compared to the 22-year NASA dataset. The regional results for Germany (DE) show an even greater sensitivity, with an increase in required overcapacity of over 170% and re-electrification storage capacity of over 175% when moving from the NASA to the ERA5 dataset. This study shows that this is not an isolated regional phenomenon but a systemic issue applicable across diverse global climate zones, from the high-latitudes of Finland (FI) to the tropical environments of Brazil (BR-SE), all of which exhibit a similar need for a more robust system design when longer time series are used. To further ensure that these differences are not solely an artefact of the different time periods, a direct comparison was conducted using both datasets for the same overlapping period of 1984-2005. As detailed in supplementary material 1, this like-for-like comparison confirms that inherent differences in the reanalysis models themselves contribute to the divergent outcomes, though the primary driver for the increased system requirements remains the extended length of the ERA5 dataset. The ‘cost of robustness’ revealed by the ERA5 data is, in effect, the cost of insuring the energy system against HILP energy droughts that are statistically unlikely to be captured in shorter datasets [30,31]. These events are not limited to short-term, synoptic-scale periods of low generation, but include multi-season or multi-year periods of VRE resource scarcity that define the true scale of the IAS challenge [37]. The failure to account for this deep variability, as demonstrated by Zeyringer et al. [24], can lead to systems that appear cost-optimal on paper but are operationally inadequate in reality when faced with real-world climate patterns.

The planning implications of this data dependency are significant. Energy infrastructure, such as pipelines, storage caverns, and power plants, has an economic and technical lifespan of 40 to 60 years or more [79,87,88]. As argued by Pfenninger [70], planning such long-lived assets based on a climate record that represents only a fraction of their operational life can lead to a sub-optimal system design and make the model results likely unreliable. It creates a false sense of security and exposes investors and society to the unpriced risk of future supply failures [64]. The financial consequences are equally severe; Collins et al. [42] showed that inter-annual weather variability could lead to a five-fold variation in system costs, a risk that is unpriced in models using shorter datasets. The findings of this study, therefore, strongly advocate for a refined approach within the specific field of IAS analysis. The use of near-centennial weather datasets, such as ERA5, should become the standard for any serious techno-economic assessment of long-duration energy storage and highly RE systems. While computationally more demanding, this approach is the only way to move beyond planning for the average and allow planning for a more realistic case, ensuring that the multi-trillion-euro investments required for the global energy transition result in systems that are not just sustainable, but also genuinely resilient over their entire operational lifetime.

5.2 Technology selection criteria for electricity balancing

The selection of an optimal energy carrier for IAS is a complex, multi-criteria decision that extends beyond a simple comparison of round-trip efficiencies. The global techno-economic assessment conducted in this study, directly comparing e-H₂ and e-CH₄, reveals that while efficiency is an important parameter, the costs associated with large-scale geological storage and the compatibility with existing infrastructure are the decisive factors. The results unequivocally show that the e-CH₄ pathway is the more economically viable option in almost all regions and scenarios, with a global annualised cost approximately 70% lower than that of the e-H₂ system. The global results presented herein provide a robust confirmation of previous regional analyses. For instance, Diesing et al. [52] demonstrated for the UK and Ireland that the additional system cost to provide IAS via e-CH₄ is 50-65% lower than for e-H₂. The strong alignment between the global findings of this study and this regional result offers a clear verdict on the central trade-off between the two leading PtGtP route candidates.

From a purely thermodynamic standpoint, the direct e-H₂ pathway is superior. The process chain, which avoids the energy-intensive and exothermic methanation step, results in a higher round-trip efficiency, calculated in this study to be 33%. This efficiency aligns with figures in the literature, which typically place the efficiency of an advanced e-H₂ cycle at around 38% [50]. The e-CH₄ pathway, which requires the additional conversion of H₂ and CO₂ into CH₄, has an inherently lower round-trip efficiency of 27%, a direct consequence of the ~80% efficiency of the methanation process itself [47]. If efficiency were the sole criterion, e-H₂ would be the clear choice. However, the scale of IAS required for a 100% RE system, with a primary energy demand of up to about 400,000 TWh globally by 2100 [89], means that the specific capex of the storage volume becomes a dominant component of the total system cost,

fundamentally altering the economic calculation. This aligns with the findings of Diesing et al. [52], who noted that the higher capex for hydrogen storage overcompensate for the additional costs of the methanation process.

This is where the decisive advantage of e-CH₄ emerges. The capex for geologically storing methane is substantially lower than that for hydrogen. While this study models the use of salt caverns, rock caverns, and underground pipelines for both e-H₂ and e-CH₄, the specific capex for hydrogen is systematically higher for each of these options. As detailed in Table 3, the capex for hydrogen storage in salt caverns is 1.03 €/kWh_{th,LHV}, compared to 0.23 €/kWh_{th,LHV} for methane, a more than four-fold difference [54,79]. The cost disparity is rooted in fundamental physical and infrastructural challenges. Hydrogen, as the smallest molecule, poses significant containment challenges, requiring more robust materials and higher compression energy to prevent leakage, particularly in porous rock formations [90,91]. While salt caverns are considered a highly secure option for hydrogen, they are geographically scarce compared to the vast, globally distributed, and well-characterised depleted oil and gas fields that are perfectly suited for methane storage [79]. Although not explicitly modelled as a distinct storage type in this study, the widespread availability of these ultra-low-cost reservoirs for methane represents a significant portfolio advantage that is not available for hydrogen, where risks of microbial conversion, contamination, and complex mixing behaviours in porous reservoirs are a major concern [92,93].

Beyond storage, e-CH₄ offers unparalleled compatibility with the vast, multi-trillion-euro natural gas infrastructure already in place [72]. As a drop-in replacement for natural gas, e-CH₄ can be transported through the existing pipeline network without significant modification [47,72]. In contrast, transporting pure hydrogen requires the construction of a new, dedicated pipeline infrastructure built from specialised materials to mitigate issues of hydrogen embrittlement, or the costly retrofitting of existing gas grids, which is often considered technically and economically challenging due to significant safety and reliability considerations [94–97]. However, repurposing existing natural gas pipelines is a viable intermediate step, with recent analyses estimating that the cost of such retrofitting is 10-50% of constructing new dedicated hydrogen pipelines, which in turn can lead to a 30-75% lower levelised cost of transport [98–100]. The ability to leverage existing assets can both avoid massive capex and provide a more gradual and politically tenable pathway for the energy transition. The findings of this study, that the e-CH₄ pathway is significantly more cost-effective, demonstrate that these infrastructure and storage cost advantages are more than sufficient to compensate for its lower round-trip efficiency.

It is important to contextualise this finding within the broader Power-to-X Economy landscape [101]. The choice of an energy carrier is highly application-specific, and while this study finds e-CH₄ to be the superior choice for the domestic bulk electricity balancing, the discourse around other carriers, such as e-MeOH, is ongoing. Brown and Hampp [50] propose e-MeOH as a compelling solution for ultra-long-duration energy storage precisely because it overcomes

the geographical limitations of geological storage. As a liquid at ambient temperature, e-MeOH can be stored in large aboveground tanks, making it a viable option for regions, i.e., large parts of Africa, southeast Europe and southeast Asia, that lack salt cavern formations required for low-cost hydrogen storage. These suitable geological formations include both salt caverns and hard rock formations [79].

Brown and Hampp [50] also highlight the drawbacks of other carriers that led them to favour e-MeOH. While similar to methanol, e-CH₄ storage requires specific geology, and any leakage is of high concern due to its potency as a greenhouse gas. For e-NH₃, high toxicity creates significant regulatory and handling challenges, and its re-conversion to electricity is hindered by the immaturity of pure ammonia turbines and the need to mitigate nitrogen oxide emissions [74]. However, for the specific application of domestic grid balancing, the e-MeOH pathway is equally limited as e-CH₄ since a sustainable CO₂ source is required for both, either as sustainable or non-avoidable point source or via direct air capture [102,103].

Therefore, while e-NH₃ and e-MeOH are leading candidates to facilitate long-distance energy trade and defossilising the shipping and aviation segments [74,104,105], their reliance on more complex synthesis and re-conversion pathways makes them less direct and efficient solutions for the specific challenge of large-scale IAS for electricity balancing. In an integrated global energy system, a portfolio of these carriers will be needed, each serving the segment where its specific properties provide the greatest value. The focus of this study on the direct e-H₂ versus e-CH₄ trade-off addresses the core competition to provide domestic large-scale energy system resilience.

5.3 Navigating the cost-resilience trade-off for energy policy

A persistent challenge in energy system planning is bridging the gap between the complex outputs of optimisation models and the practical needs of policymakers, who must select a single, defensible investment pathway [56]. While multi-objective models effectively generate a Pareto front illustrating the full spectrum of optimal trade-offs, corner solutions are often highlighted, such as in Brown and Hampp [50], Diesing et al. [52], and Hasan et al. [57], leaving the continuum of compromise solutions largely unexplored. The tau-analogy introduced in this study offers a transparent and systematic heuristic to navigate this decision-making landscape, identifying practical implementation pathways that balance economic efficiency with physical resilience.

The analysis of the Pareto fronts in this study confirms the classic trade-off, highlighting that systems designed for minimum VRE overcapacity are reliable but incur a high cost markup, while systems designed for absolute minimum cost require large levels of overcapacity that may be impractical due to land-use constraints [5], supply chain limitations [106,107], or social acceptance issues [108]. The tau-analogy provides a structured method to identify points of significant diminishing returns along this curve. This is particularly relevant given the economic challenges highlighted by Öberg et al. [63], who found that infrequently used balancing assets struggle with cost recovery, underscoring the need for balanced system

designs that avoid excessive investment in such technologies. The results show that the τ_1 solution, which captures 63.2% of the total possible cost reduction, consistently represents a highly attractive ‘knee’ on the Pareto curve for all regions and technologies. The effectiveness of this trade-off is particularly striking in regions with high initial costs. For instance, in the e-CH₄ with ERA5 weather data scenario for Java and Timor Leste (ID-JV+TL), a modest 2%_{abs} increase in overcapacity to reach the τ_1 solution cuts the ACOIAS cost markup by more than half, from a prohibitive 271% down to 103%. This result demonstrates that a small, targeted investment in VRE overcapacity can yield a disproportionately large reduction in IAS system cost, a finding that is crucial when building a political and business case for such investments.

This approach aligns with a growing body of research that advocates for moving beyond a singular focus on the absolute cost-optimum and instead exploring the near-optimal feasible space [109]. Solutions in this space may be only marginally more expensive than the absolute optimum but can offer significant co-benefits in terms of reduced infrastructure build-out, lower resource dependency, enhanced system robustness, and overall energy security [110]. The τ_2 (86.5% cost reduction) and τ_3 (95% cost reduction) solutions presented in this study provide policymakers with a clear, tiered set of options to quantify this trade-off. For example, in the e-H₂ with ERA5 data scenario for Chile (CL), the τ_2 solution reduces the IAS cost markup from a prohibitive 175% with 2.1% overcapacity to a more tenable 27% with 4.1% overcapacity. Policymakers can then assess the final step to the τ_3 solution, which offers a further cost reduction to 12%, but requires increasing the overcapacity to 4.9%. This highlights a critical decision point where a marginal 0.8%_{abs} increase in infrastructure build-out yields a progressively smaller economic gain.

5.4 Study limitations and future research directions

While this study provides a robust global analysis of key trade-offs for IAS, its methodological boundaries define a clear scope for future research. The primary limitations relate to the assumptions regarding system boundaries, the scope of RE and flexibility options, the static nature of the climate data, and the purely techno-economic focus of the optimisation.

First, the analysis treats each of the 145 global regions as an isolated energy system, neglecting the significant balancing effects of cross-border energy trade. Extensive research has demonstrated that enhanced grid interconnection is a highly effective measure for smoothing VRE variability, reducing the need for storage and curtailment by allowing regions to share diverse resources [21,23,111]. Future work should integrate inter-regional energy exchange, both via electricity grids and dedicated pipelines for hydrogen or methane, which is expected to lower overall IAS requirements and potentially alter the relative cost-effectiveness of different storage carriers on a continental scale [109].

A related limitation arises from the differing geographical scope of the two weather dataset analyses. While the baseline assessment using the 22-year NASA dataset was conducted for all 145 global regions, the in-depth analysis with the computationally intensive 85-year ERA5 dataset was focused on 14 representative regions. Although these regions were carefully

selected to cover a wide range of global climatic conditions and energy system archetypes, a full 145-region analysis with the ERA5 data would provide a more granular picture of how long-term variability impacts every unique geography. However, the consistency of the findings across the diverse sample of 14 regions provides high confidence that the core conclusions are globally applicable. Future research, leveraging increasing computational power, could expand the 85-year analysis to all 145 regions to validate these findings at the highest possible geographical resolution.

Second, this study focuses on the IAV of solar and wind resources alone. A more comprehensive analysis would incorporate the variability of other key RE, particularly hydropower, which is known to be highly sensitive to multi-year climate patterns such as the El Niño-Southern Oscillation and can be a major driver of inter-annual energy deficits in hydropower-rich regions [112]. Furthermore, the model does not include demand-side management (DSM) as a flexibility option to manage inter-annual deficits. While DSM is typically viewed as a tool for short-term balancing, strategic industrial load shifting or flexible hydrogen production could potentially reduce the need for supply-side storage over longer timescales, a research area that remains under-explored [14]. Another possible energy sector for DSM would be a large-scale carbon dioxide removal sector beyond 2050 [89,113].

Third, the use of historical weather data, even over an 85-year period, does not account for the projected impacts of future climate change. A growing body of literature indicates that climate change may alter the mean availability and variability of VRE resources, with complex regional effects on wind speeds and solar irradiation [114,115]. Future studies should integrate downscaled climate projections to assess the resilience of these IAS-dependent systems under non-stationary climate conditions, ensuring that infrastructure planned today remains robust throughout the latter half of the 21st century.

Finally, this analysis is purely techno-economic and does not consider socio-political factors that can be decisive for real-world project implementation. Scenarios requiring high levels of VRE overcapacity may face significant practical barriers related to land-use conflicts, supply chain limitations for critical materials, and social acceptance [5,106,108]. Future research should aim to integrate these soft constraints into energy system models to produce results that are not only cost-optimal but also politically and socially feasible. Expanding the technology comparison to include other carriers, i.e., e-MeOH or e-NH₃, particularly in the context of integrated energy systems that serve both grid balancing and fuel export functions, also remains a promising avenue for future investigation. Addressing these limitations will be crucial for developing a fully comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities for ensuring the resilience of a global 100% RE system.

6. Conclusions

This study conducted a comprehensive global techno-economic analysis to address three critical and interconnected challenges in planning for 100% renewable energy systems, namely

the impact of weather data series length, the selection of the optimal chemical energy carrier for inter-annual storage, and the need for practical multi-objective decision-making frameworks. The analysis, comparing electricity-based hydrogen and electricity-based methane across a 22-year and an 85-year weather dataset, yields primary conclusions that have significant implications for the future of the global energy transition.

A definitive techno-economic comparison reveals that for the specific application of providing bulk, inter-annual electricity balancing, electricity-based methane is the more cost-effective energy carrier than electricity-based hydrogen in almost all global regions. The global annualised cost of an inter-annual storage system based on e-methane was found to be approximately 74% lower than for a system based on e-hydrogen. This decisive economic advantage is driven almost entirely by the substantially lower capital expenditure of geological storage for methane, which more than compensates for the higher round-trip efficiency of the direct hydrogen pathway. This finding suggests that leveraging existing natural gas infrastructure and developing cost-effective methanation technologies is a more financially sustainable strategy to ensure domestic energy system resilience than building out a parallel hydrogen storage and transport network.

Furthermore, this research provides a robust, quantitative confirmation that the length of the historical weather data used in energy system models has a profound impact on optimal system design and cost. The use of an extensive 85-year weather dataset consistently resulted in systems requiring significantly more infrastructure. In the curtailment-optimised case, planning with the longer dataset increased the required variable renewable energy overcapacity by 57% and the inter-annual storage volume by 58% on a global demand-weighted average, for both the e-hydrogen and e-methane scenarios, compared to the system planned with the 22-year dataset. The demand-weighted global cost markup increases from 110% to 167% for the e-hydrogen scenario and from 30% to 45% for the e-methane scenario, respectively, when transitioning from the 22-year to the 85-year case, compared to the single year case. This physical under-planning directly translates to a significant financial surcharge, increasing the system cost markup by 58% for the e-hydrogen pathway and 59% for the e-methane pathway.

For the cost-optimised case, ensuring resiliency against the full 85-year weather data increases the required overcapacity by a global demand-weighted average of 55%, with the increase for the 14 investigated regions ranging from 3% to 173%. Similarly, the annualised cost of the inter-annual balancing system increased by a global average of 57% compared to the 22-year data, with a regional range of 6% to 149%, in reference to the 2.9% demand-weighted global cost markup for both e-hydrogen and e-methane, of the 22-year inter-annual balancing compared to the single year case. This demonstrates that planning with shorter time series, which may not capture the full extent of high-impact, low-probability energy droughts, leads to a systematic and substantial underestimation of the physical infrastructure and financial investment required to guarantee long-term security of supply.

Finally, this study introduces and applies the 'tau-analogy' as a novel, transparent, and systematic heuristic to navigate the complex trade-offs on the cost-overcapacity Pareto front. The analysis demonstrates that it is possible to achieve the vast majority of potential cost savings without committing to the extreme levels of overcapacity required by a pure cost-optimisation. The identified tau solutions provide policymakers with a clear framework for selecting pragmatic and politically tenable compromise solutions that balance economic efficiency with practical constraints on land use and resource deployment.

Ultimately, this study underscores that the successful transition to a fully renewable global energy system hinges on planning methodologies that are as robust and resilient as the infrastructure they are designed to create. By accounting for deep climate variability and making pragmatic technological choices, it is possible to design the financially sustainable and physically reliable energy systems required for a net-zero emissions future.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability statement

Data are provided in the appendix and supplementary material of this study.

References

- [1] [UNFCCC] United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, Report of the Conference of the Parties on its Twenty-First Session FCCC/CP/2015/10/Add.1, Paris, 2015. <https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/2015/cop21/eng/109r01.pdf> (accessed January 23, 2025).
- [2] [IRENA] International Renewable Energy Agency, Renewable Capacity Highlights 2025, Abu Dhabi, 2025. https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2025/Jul/IRENA_DAT_Renewable_energy_highlights_2025.pdf.
- [3] [IRENA] International Renewable Energy Agency. Renewable capacity statistics 2025, Abu Dhabi, (2025). <https://www.irena.org/Publications/2025/Mar/Renewable-capacity-statistics-2025> (accessed July 11, 2025).

- [4] D. Bogdanov, M. Ram, A. Aghahosseini, A. Gulagi, A.S. Oyewo, M. Child, U. Caldera, K. Sadovskaia, J. Farfan, L. De Souza Noel Simas Barbosa, M. Fasihi, S. Khalili, T. Traber, C. Breyer, Low-cost renewable electricity as the key driver of the global energy transition towards sustainability, *Energy* 227 (2021) 120467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.120467>.
- [5] C. Breyer, S. Khalili, D. Bogdanov, M. Ram, A.S. Oyewo, A. Aghahosseini, A. Gulagi, A.A. Solomon, D. Keiner, G. Lopez, P.A. Østergaard, H. Lund, B.V. Mathiesen, M.Z. Jacobson, M. Victoria, S. Teske, T. Pregger, V. Fthenakis, M. Raugei, H. Holttinen, U. Bardi, A. Hoekstra, B.K. Sovacool, On the History and Future of 100% Renewable Energy Systems Research, *IEEE Access* 10 (2022) 78176–78218. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3193402>.
- [6] Z. Dalala, M. Al-Omari, M. Al-Addous, M. Bdour, Y. Al-Khasawneh, M. Alkasrawi, Increased renewable energy penetration in national electrical grids constraints and solutions, *Energy* 246 (2022) 123361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.123361>.
- [7] G. Luderer, S. Madeddu, L. Merfort, F. Ueckerdt, M. Pehl, R. Pietzcker, M. Rottoli, F. Schreyer, N. Bauer, L. Baumstark, C. Bertram, A. Dirnaichner, F. Humpenöder, A. Levesque, A. Popp, R. Rodrigues, J. Strefler, E. Kriegler, Impact of declining renewable energy costs on electrification in low-emission scenarios, *Nat Energy* 7 (2022) 32–42. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00937-z>.
- [8] S. Khalili, C. Breyer, Review on 100% Renewable Energy System Analyses—A Bibliometric Perspective, *IEEE Access* 10 (2022) 125792–125834. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3221155>.
- [9] S. Khalili, G. Lopez, C. Breyer, Role and trends of flexibility options in 100% renewable energy system analyses towards the Power-to-X Economy, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 212 (2025) 115383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.115383>.
- [10] F. Ueckerdt, R. Brecha, G. Luderer, Analyzing major challenges of wind and solar variability in power systems, *Renewable Energy* 81 (2015) 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2015.03.002>.
- [11] D. Lew, D. Bartlett, A. Groom, P. Jorgensen, J. O’Sullivan, R. Quint, B. Rew, B. Rockwell, S. Sharma, Getting to 100% renewables: operating experiences with very high penetrations of variable energy resources, *IET Renewable Power Generation* 14 (2020) 3899–3907. <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-rpg.2020.0573>.
- [12] T.O. Olowu, A. Sundararajan, M. Moghaddami, A.I. Sarwat, Future Challenges and Mitigation Methods for High Photovoltaic Penetration: A Survey, *Energies* 11 (2018) 1782. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11071782>.
- [13] F.M. Mulder, Implications of diurnal and seasonal variations in renewable energy generation for large scale energy storage, *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy* 6 (2014) 033105. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4874845>.
- [14] P.D. Lund, J. Lindgren, J. Mikkola, J. Salpakari, Review of energy system flexibility measures to enable high levels of variable renewable electricity, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 45 (2015) 785–807. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.01.057>.
- [15] H. Lund, P.A. Østergaard, D. Connolly, I. Ridjan, B.V. Mathiesen, F. Hvelplund, J.Z. Thellufsen, P. Sorknæs, Energy Storage and Smart Energy Systems, *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management* 11 (2016) 3–14. <https://doi.org/10.5278/ijsep.2016.11.2>.
- [16] K.M. Tan, V.K. Ramachandramurthy, J.Y. Yong, Integration of electric vehicles in smart grid: A review on vehicle to grid technologies and optimization techniques, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 53 (2016) 720–732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.09.012>.

- [17] A. Kies, B.U. Schyska, L. Von Bremen, The Demand Side Management Potential to Balance a Highly Renewable European Power System, *Energies* 9 (2016) 955. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9110955>.
- [18] I. Atzeni, L.G. Ordóñez, G. Scutari, D.P. Palomar, J.R. Fonollosa, Demand-Side Management via Distributed Energy Generation and Storage Optimization, *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid* 4 (2013) 866–876. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2012.2206060>.
- [19] D. Groppi, A. Pfeifer, D.A. Garcia, G. Krajačić, N. Duić, A review on energy storage and demand side management solutions in smart energy islands, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 135 (2021) 110183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.110183>.
- [20] J.C. Osorio-Aravena, A. Aghahosseini, D. Bogdanov, U. Caldera, N. Ghorbani, T.N.O. Mensah, J. Haas, E. Muñoz-Cerón, C. Breyer, Synergies of electrical and sectoral integration: Analysing geographical multi-node scenarios with sector coupling variations for a transition towards a fully renewables-based energy system, *Energy* 279 (2023) 128038. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.128038>.
- [21] T. Brown, D. Schlachtberger, A. Kies, S. Schramm, M. Greiner, Synergies of sector coupling and transmission reinforcement in a cost-optimised, highly renewable European energy system, *Energy* 160 (2018) 720–739. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.06.222>.
- [22] J. Gea-Bermúdez, I.G. Jensen, M. Münster, M. Koivisto, J.G. Kirkerud, Y. Chen, H. Ravn, The role of sector coupling in the green transition: A least-cost energy system development in Northern-central Europe towards 2050, *Applied Energy* 289 (2021) 116685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116685>.
- [23] R.A. Rodríguez, S. Becker, G.B. Andresen, D. Heide, M. Greiner, Transmission needs across a fully renewable European power system, *Renewable Energy* 63 (2014) 467–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2013.10.005>.
- [24] M. Zeyringer, J. Price, B. Fais, P.-H. Li, E. Sharp, Designing low-carbon power systems for Great Britain in 2050 that are robust to the spatiotemporal and inter-annual variability of weather, *Nat Energy* 3 (2018) 395–403. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0128-x>.
- [25] M. Jafari, M. Korpås, A. Botterud, Power system decarbonization: Impacts of energy storage duration and interannual renewables variability, *Renewable Energy* 156 (2020) 1171–1185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.04.144>.
- [26] [IEA] International Energy Agency Managing Seasonal and Interannual Variability of Renewables, Paris, IEA (2023). <https://www.iea.org/reports/managing-seasonal-and-interannual-variability-of-renewables> (accessed July 5, 2025).
- [27] L. van der Most, K. van der Wiel, R.M.J. Benders, P.W. Gerbens-Leenes, R. Bintanja, Impacts of future changes in climate variability on Europe’s renewable electricity systems, *Environ. Res.: Climate* 4 (2025) 025007. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2752-5295/add613>.
- [28] J. Novacheck, M. Schwarz, G. Buster, A Weather Analysis for Xcel Energy’s 2030 Colorado Preferred Plan, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.2172/2323481>.
- [29] S.C. Pryor, T.J. Shepherd, R.J. Barthelmie, Interannual variability of wind climates and wind turbine annual energy production, *Wind Energy Science* 3 (2018) 651–665. <https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-3-651-2018>.
- [30] M. Panteli, C. Pickering, S. Wilkinson, R. Dawson, P. Mancarella, Power System Resilience to Extreme Weather: Fragility Modeling, Probabilistic Impact Assessment, and Adaptation Measures, *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 32 (2017) 3747–3757. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2016.2641463>.
- [31] C. Bracken, N. Voisin, C.D. Burleyson, A.M. Campbell, Z.J. Hou, D. Broman, Standardized benchmark of historical compound wind and solar energy droughts across the

- Continental United States, *Renewable Energy* 220 (2024) 119550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.119550>.
- [32] A. Gangopadhyay, A.K. Seshadri, N.J. Sparks, R. Toumi, The role of wind-solar hybrid plants in mitigating renewable energy-droughts, *Renewable Energy* 194 (2022) 926–937. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.05.122>.
- [33] B. Li, S. Basu, S.J. Watson, H.W.J. Russchenberg, A Brief Climatology of Dunkelflaute Events over and Surrounding the North and Baltic Sea Areas, *Energies* 14 (2021) 6508. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14206508>.
- [34] M. Kittel, W.-P. Schill, Measuring the Dunkelflaute: how (not) to analyze variable renewable energy shortage, *Environ. Res.: Energy* 1 (2024) 035007. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2753-3751/ad6dfc>.
- [35] F. Mockert, C.M. Grams, T. Brown, F. Neumann, Meteorological conditions during periods of low wind speed and insolation in Germany: The role of weather regimes, *Meteorological Applications* 30 (2023) e2141. <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.2141>.
- [36] T.W. Brown, T. Bischof-Niemz, K. Blok, C. Breyer, H. Lund, B.V. Mathiesen, Response to ‘Burden of proof: A comprehensive review of the feasibility of 100% renewable-electricity systems,’ *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 92 (2018) 834–847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.04.113>.
- [37] O. Ruhnau, S. Qvist, Storage requirements in a 100% renewable electricity system: extreme events and inter-annual variability, *Environ. Res. Lett.* 17 (2022) 044018. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac4dc8>.
- [38] B. Cárdenas, L. Swinfen-Styles, J. Rouse, S.D. Garvey, Short-, Medium-, and Long-Duration Energy Storage in a 100% Renewable Electricity Grid: A UK Case Study, *Energies* 14 (2021) 8524. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14248524>.
- [39] J.A. Dowling, K.Z. Rinaldi, T.H. Ruggles, S.J. Davis, M. Yuan, F. Tong, N.S. Lewis, K. Caldeira, Role of Long-Duration Energy Storage in Variable Renewable Electricity Systems, *Joule* 4 (2020) 1907–1928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.07.007>.
- [40] O.H. Hohmeyer, S. Bohm, Trends toward 100% renewable electricity supply in Germany and Europe: a paradigm shift in energy policies, *WIREs Energy and Environment* 4 (2015) 74–97. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.128>.
- [41] Y. Zeng, T. Zhou, T. Wang, M. Zhang, S. Zhang, H. Yang, Long-Duration Energy Storage: A Critical Enabler for Renewable Integration and Decarbonization, *Energies* 18 (2025) 466. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18030466>.
- [42] S. Collins, P. Deane, B.Ó. Gallachóir, S. Pfenninger, I. Staffell, Impacts of Inter-annual Wind and Solar Variations on the European Power System, *Joule* 2 (2018) 2076–2090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2018.06.020>.
- [43] H.C. Bloomfield, P.L.M. Gonzalez, J.K. Lundquist, L.P. Stoop, J. Browell, R. Dargaville, M.D. Felice, K. Gruber, A. Hilbers, A. Kies, M. Panteli, H.E. Thornton, J. Wohland, M. Zeyringer, D.J. Brayshaw, The Importance of Weather and Climate to Energy Systems: A Workshop on Next Generation Challenges in Energy–Climate Modeling, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0256.1>.
- [44] B.M. Fekete, M. Bacskó, J. Zhang, M. Chen, Storage requirements to mitigate intermittent renewable energy sources: analysis for the US Northeast, *Front. Environ. Sci.* 11 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1076830>.
- [45] J.M. Wilczak, D.B. Kirk-Davidoff, H. Bloomfield, C. Bracken, J. Sharp, Wind and solar energy droughts: Potential impacts on energy system dynamics and research needs, *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy* 17 (2025) 022301. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0253058>.

- [46] M. Sterner, M. Specht, Power-to-Gas and Power-to-X—The History and Results of Developing a New Storage Concept, *Energies* 14 (2021) 6594. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14206594>.
- [47] M. Götz, J. Lefebvre, F. Mörs, A. McDaniel Koch, F. Graf, S. Bajohr, R. Reimert, T. Kolb, Renewable Power-to-Gas: A technological and economic review, *Renewable Energy* 85 (2016) 1371–1390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2015.07.066>.
- [48] M. Bailera, P. Lisbona, L.M. Romeo, S. Espatolero, Power to Gas projects review: Lab, pilot and demo plants for storing renewable energy and CO₂, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 69 (2017) 292–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.130>.
- [49] M. Fasihi, C. Breyer, Baseload electricity and hydrogen supply based on hybrid PV-wind power plants, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 243 (2020) 118466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118466>.
- [50] T. Brown, J. Hampp, Ultra-long-duration energy storage anywhere: Methanol with carbon cycling, *Joule* 7 (2023) 2414–2420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2023.10.001>.
- [51] C. Tsiklios, S. Schneider, M. Hermesmann, T.E. Müller, Efficiency and optimal load capacity of E-Fuel-Based energy storage systems, *Advances in Applied Energy* 10 (2023) 100140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adapen.2023.100140>.
- [52] P. Diesing, D. Bogdanov, D. Keiner, R. Satymov, D. Toke, C. Breyer, Exploring the demand for inter-annual storage for balancing wind energy variability in 100% renewable energy systems, *Energy* 312 (2024) 133572. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.133572>.
- [53] H. Blanco, A. Faaij, A review at the role of storage in energy systems with a focus on Power to Gas and long-term storage, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 81 (2018) 1049–1086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.07.062>.
- [54] M. Fasihi, R. Weiss, J. Savolainen, C. Breyer, Global potential of green ammonia based on hybrid PV-wind power plants, *Applied Energy* 294 (2021) 116170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116170>.
- [55] M. Fasihi, C. Breyer, Global production potential of green methanol based on variable renewable electricity, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 17 (2024) 3503–3522. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EE02951D>.
- [56] C.H. Antunes, C.O. Henriques, Multi-Objective Optimization and Multi-Criteria Analysis Models and Methods for Problems in the Energy Sector, in: S. Greco, M. Ehrgott, J.R. Figueira (Eds.), *Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis: State of the Art Surveys*, Springer, New York, NY, 2016: pp. 1067–1165. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-3094-4_25.
- [57] M.H. Hasan, D. Keiner, C. Breyer, Techno-economic analysis of inter-annual energy storage and overcapacity in 100 % renewable energy systems for 145 regions globally, *Applied Energy* 401 (2025) 126736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2025.126736>.
- [58] B.P. Heard, B.W. Brook, T.M.L. Wigley, C.J.A. Bradshaw, Burden of proof: A comprehensive review of the feasibility of 100% renewable-electricity systems, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 76 (2017) 1122–1133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.03.114>.
- [59] M. Beaudin, H. Zareipour, A. Schellenberglabe, W. Rosehart, Energy storage for mitigating the variability of renewable electricity sources: An updated review, *Energy for Sustainable Development* 14 (2010) 302–314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2010.09.007>.
- [60] J. Widén, N. Carpman, V. Castellucci, D. Lingfors, J. Olauson, F. Remouit, M. Bergkvist, M. Grabbe, R. Waters, Variability assessment and forecasting of renewables: A review for solar, wind, wave and tidal resources, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 44 (2015) 356–375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.12.019>.

- [61] A.-K. Gerlach, D. Stetter, J. Schmid, C. Breyer, PV and Wind Power – Complementary Technologies, in: Proceedings of the ISES Solar World Congress 2011, International Solar Energy Society, Kassel, Germany, 2011: pp. 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.18086/swc.2011.16.04>.
- [62] B. Cárdenas, L. Swinfen-Styles, J. Rouse, A. Hoskin, W. Xu, S.D. Garvey, Energy storage capacity vs. renewable penetration: A study for the UK, *Renewable Energy* 171 (2021) 849–867. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.02.149>.
- [63] S. Öberg, F. Johnsson, M. Odenberger, The impact of inter-annual weather variations on energy storage and flexible generation – a UK case study, *Energy* 335 (2025) 137780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2025.137780>.
- [64] E.K. Gøtske, G.B. Andresen, F. Neumann, M. Victoria, Designing a sector-coupled European energy system robust to 60 years of historical weather data, *Nat Commun* 15 (2024) 10680. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-54853-3>.
- [65] S. Pfenninger, I. Staffell, Long-term patterns of European PV output using 30 years of validated hourly reanalysis and satellite data, *Energy* 114 (2016) 1251–1265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2016.08.060>.
- [66] H.C. Bloomfield, D.J. Brayshaw, M. Deakin, D. Greenwood, Hourly historical and near-future weather and climate variables for energy system modelling, *Earth System Science Data* 14 (2022) 2749–2766. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-14-2749-2022>.
- [67] D.J. Cannon, D.J. Brayshaw, J. Methven, P.J. Coker, D. Lenaghan, Using reanalysis data to quantify extreme wind power generation statistics: A 33 year case study in Great Britain, *Renewable Energy* 75 (2015) 767–778. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.10.024>.
- [68] P. Minnis, E.F. Harrison, L.L. Stowe, G.G. Gibson, F.M. Denn, D.R. Doelling, W.L. Smith, Radiative Climate Forcing by the Mount Pinatubo Eruption, *Science* 259 (1993) 1411–1415. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.259.5100.1411>.
- [69] A.R. Varne, S. Blouin, B.L.M. Williams, D. Denkenberger, The Impact of Abrupt Sunlight Reduction Scenarios on Renewable Energy Production, *Energies* 17 (2024) 5147. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17205147>.
- [70] S. Pfenninger, Dealing with multiple decades of hourly wind and PV time series in energy models: A comparison of methods to reduce time resolution and the planning implications of inter-annual variability, *Applied Energy* 197 (2017) 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.03.051>.
- [71] G. Pleßmann, M. Erdmann, M. Hlusiak, C. Breyer, Global Energy Storage Demand for a 100% Renewable Electricity Supply, *Energy Procedia* 46 (2014) 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.01.154>.
- [72] S. Schiebahn, T. Grube, M. Robinius, V. Tietze, B. Kumar, D. Stolten, Power to gas: Technological overview, systems analysis and economic assessment for a case study in Germany, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 40 (2015) 4285–4294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.01.123>.
- [73] O.J. Guerra, J. Zhang, J. Eichman, P. Denholm, J. Kurtz, B.-M. Hodge, The value of seasonal energy storage technologies for the integration of wind and solar power, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 13 (2020) 1909–1922. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EE00771D>.
- [74] A. Valera-Medina, H. Xiao, M. Owen-Jones, W.I.F. David, P.J. Bowen, Ammonia for power, *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science* 69 (2018) 63–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2018.07.001>.
- [75] A. Nemmour, A. Inayat, I. Janajreh, C. Ghenai, Green hydrogen-based E-fuels (E-methane, E-methanol, E-ammonia) to support clean energy transition: A literature review, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 48 (2023) 29011–29033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.03.240>.

- [76] M.S. Javed, J. Jurasz, M. Guezgouz, F.A. Canales, T.H. Ruggles, T. Ma, Impact of multi-annual renewable energy variability on the optimal sizing of off-grid systems, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 183 (2023) 113514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113514>.
- [77] The Math Works Inc. (2024). MATLAB 2024b. Natick., (2024). <https://www.mathworks.com/> (accessed January 13, 2025).
- [78] C. Breyer, E. Tsupari, V. Tikka, P. Vainikka, Power-to-Gas as an Emerging Profitable Business Through Creating an Integrated Value Chain, *Energy Procedia* 73 (2015) 182–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2015.07.668>.
- [79] A. Aghahosseini, C. Breyer, Assessment of geological resource potential for compressed air energy storage in global electricity supply, *Energy Conversion and Management* 169 (2018) 161–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.05.058>.
- [80] Langley Research Center, ed., NASA Surface Meteorology and Solar Energy: Global Data Sets, Release 6.0, NASA Langley Research Center, Hampton, Va, 2007. https://earthworks.stanford.edu/?f%5Baccess%5D%5B%5D=public&f%5Bdc_publisher_s%5D%5B%5D=NASA+Langley+Atmospheric+Sciences+Data+Center&f%5Bdct_provenance_s%5D%5B%5D=Stanford&f%5Bsolr_year_i%5D%5B%5D=1983 (accessed January 14, 2025).
- [81] Stackhouse PW, Whitlock CH. Surface meteorology and solar energy (SSE) release 6.0 Methodology, NASA SSE 6.0; Langley, (2009). <https://power.larc.nasa.gov/docs/methodology/> (accessed January 14, 2025).
- [82] D. Stetter, Enhancement of the REMix energy system model : global renewable energy potentials, optimized power plant siting and scenario validation, thesis, Universität Stuttgart, 2014. <http://elib.uni-stuttgart.de/opus/volltexte/2014/9453/> (accessed January 14, 2025).
- [83] Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J.-N. (2023): ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), n.d. <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47>.
- [84] D. Keiner, L. Walter, D. Bogdanov, I.M. Peters, C. Breyer, Assessing the impact of bifacial solar photovoltaics on future power systems based on capacity-density-optimised power plant yield modelling, *Solar Energy* 295 (2025) 113543. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2025.113543>.
- [85] R. Satymov, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, Global-local analysis of cost-optimal onshore wind turbine configurations considering wind classes and hub heights, *Energy* 256 (2022) 124629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.124629>.
- [86] M. Sterner, I. Stadler, eds., *Handbook of Energy Storage: Demand, Technologies, Integration*, Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-55504-0>.
- [87] S. Afanasyeva, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, Relevance of PV with single-axis tracking for energy scenarios, *Solar Energy* 173 (2018) 173–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2018.07.029>.
- [88] [IEA] International Energy Agency Projected Costs of Generating Electricity 2020 – Analysis, Paris, IEA (2020). <https://www.iea.org/reports/projected-costs-of-generating-electricity-2020> (accessed July 9, 2025).
- [89] D. Keiner, A. Gulagi, C. Breyer, Energy demand estimation using a pre-processing macro-economic modelling tool for 21st century transition analyses, *Energy* 272 (2023) 127199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.127199>.

- [90] K. Mazloomi, C. Gomes, Hydrogen as an energy carrier: Prospects and challenges, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 16 (2012) 3024–3033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.02.028>.
- [91] M. Aslannezhad, M. Ali, A. Kalantariasl, M. Sayyafzadeh, Z. You, S. Iglauer, A. Keshavarz, A review of hydrogen/rock/brine interaction: Implications for Hydrogen Geo-storage, *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science* 95 (2023) 101066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2022.101066>.
- [92] M. Panfilov, Underground Storage of Hydrogen: In Situ Self-Organisation and Methane Generation, *Transp Porous Med* 85 (2010) 841–865. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-010-9595-7>.
- [93] T.A. Buscheck, A. Goodman, G. Lackey, J. De Toledo Camargo, N. Huerta, F. Haeri, G.M. Freeman, J.A. White, Underground storage of hydrogen and hydrogen/methane mixtures in porous reservoirs: Influence of reservoir factors and engineering choices on deliverability and storage operations, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 49 (2024) 1088–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.07.073>.
- [94] D. Haeseldonckx, W. D’haeseleer, The use of the natural-gas pipeline infrastructure for hydrogen transport in a changing market structure, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 32 (2007) 1381–1386. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2006.10.018>.
- [95] M.W. Melaina, O. Antonia, M. Penev, Blending Hydrogen into Natural Gas Pipeline Networks: A Review of Key Issues, National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), Golden, CO (United States), 2013. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1068610>.
- [96] F. Neumann, E. Zeyen, M. Victoria, T. Brown, The potential role of a hydrogen network in Europe, *Joule* 7 (2023) 1793–1817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2023.06.016>.
- [97] K.M. Groth, A. Al-Douri, Chapter 15 - Hydrogen safety, risk, and reliability analysis, in: A. Scipioni, A. Manzardo, J. Ren (Eds.), *Hydrogen Economy (Second Edition)*, Academic Press, 2023: pp. 487–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-99514-6.00012-1>.
- [98] T. Galimova, M. Fasihi, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, Impact of international transportation chains on cost of green e-hydrogen: Global cost of hydrogen and consequences for Germany and Finland, *Applied Energy* 347 (2023) 121369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121369>.
- [99] G. Brändle, M. Schönfisch, S. Schulte, Estimating long-term global supply costs for low-carbon hydrogen, *Applied Energy* 302 (2021) 117481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117481>.
- [100] A. Wang, J. Jens, D. Mavins, M. Moultak, M. Schimmel, K. van der Leun, D. Peters, M. Buseman, European Hydrogen Backbone: Analysing future demand, supply, and transport of hydrogen., Utrecht, 2021. <https://ehb.eu/files/downloads/EHB-Analysing-the-future-demand-supply-and-transport-of-hydrogen-June-2021-v3.pdf> (accessed July 15, 2025).
- [101] C. Breyer, G. Lopez, D. Bogdanov, P. Laaksonen, The role of electricity-based hydrogen in the emerging power-to-X economy, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 49 (2024) 351–359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.08.170>.
- [102] M. Fasihi, O. Efimova, C. Breyer, Techno-economic assessment of CO₂ direct air capture plants, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 224 (2019) 957–980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.03.086>.
- [103] T. Galimova, M. Ram, D. Bogdanov, M. Fasihi, S. Khalili, A. Gulagi, H. Karjunen, T.N.O. Mensah, C. Breyer, Global demand analysis for carbon dioxide as raw material from key industrial sources and direct air capture to produce renewable electricity-based fuels and chemicals, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 373 (2022) 133920. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133920>.

- [104] T. Galimova, M. Fasihi, D. Bogdanov, C. Breyer, Feasibility of green ammonia trading via pipelines and shipping: Cases of Europe, North Africa, and South America, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 427 (2023) 139212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139212>.
- [105] T. Galimova, M. Fasihi, D. Bogdanov, G. Lopez, C. Breyer, Analysis of green e-methanol supply costs: Domestic production in Europe versus imports via pipeline and sea shipping, *Renewable Energy* 241 (2025) 122336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.122336>.
- [106] V. Lundaev, A.A. Solomon, T. Le, A. Lohrmann, C. Breyer, Review of critical materials for the energy transition, an analysis of global resources and production databases and the state of material circularity, *Minerals Engineering* 203 (2023) 108282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2023.108282>.
- [107] T. Naegler, S. Rauner, A. Dirnaichner, P. Jochem, S. Schlosser, G. Luderer, Raw material demand and geopolitical risk in carbon-neutral futures, *Energy Policy* 204 (2025) 114622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2025.114622>.
- [108] A. Krumm, D. Süsser, P. Blechinger, Modelling social aspects of the energy transition: What is the current representation of social factors in energy models?, *Energy* 239 (2022) 121706. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121706>.
- [109] F. Neumann, T. Brown, The near-optimal feasible space of a renewable power system model, *Electric Power Systems Research* 190 (2021) 106690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2020.106690>.
- [110] A. Azzuni, C. Breyer, Definitions and dimensions of energy security: a literature review, *WIREs Energy and Environment* 7 (2018) e268. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.268>.
- [111] T. Galimova, M. Ram, D. Bogdanov, M. Fasihi, A. Gulagi, S. Khalili, C. Breyer, Global trading of renewable electricity-based fuels and chemicals to enhance the energy transition across all sectors towards sustainability, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 183 (2023) 113420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113420>.
- [112] E.K. Gøtske, M. Victoria, Future operation of hydropower in Europe under high renewable penetration and climate change, *iScience* 24 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2021.102999>.
- [113] A. Mühlbauer, D. Keiner, C. Gerhards, U. Caldera, M. Sterner, C. Breyer, Assessment of technologies and economics for carbon dioxide removal from a portfolio perspective, *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 141 (2025) 104297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2024.104297>.
- [114] S. Jerez, I. Tobin, R. Vautard, J.P. Montávez, J.M. López-Romero, F. Thais, B. Bartok, O.B. Christensen, A. Colette, M. Déqué, G. Nikulin, S. Kotlarski, E. van Meijgaard, C. Teichmann, M. Wild, The impact of climate change on photovoltaic power generation in Europe, *Nat Commun* 6 (2015) 10014. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10014>.
- [115] I. Tobin, R. Vautard, I. Balog, F.-M. Bréon, S. Jerez, P.M. Ruti, F. Thais, M. Vrac, P. Yiou, Assessing climate change impacts on European wind energy from ENSEMBLES high-resolution climate projections, *Climatic Change* 128 (2015) 99–112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-014-1291-0>.